

ADVANCE SOCIAL SCIENCE ARCHIVE JOURNAL

Available Online: <https://assajournal.com>
Vol. 03 No. 02. Apr-Jun 2025. Page#.1660-1678
Print ISSN: [3006-2497](https://doi.org/10.30669/3006-2497) Online ISSN: [3006-2500](https://doi.org/10.30669/3006-2500)
Platform & Workflow by: [Open Journal Systems](https://openjournal.org/)

Investigating the Impacts of Motivation on English Language Learning: A Comparative Study of Integrative and Instrumental Motivation among English Undergraduate Students at the

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Abstract

This study investigates the impacts of motivation on English language learning among English undergraduate students at the University of Lakki Marwat (ULM), with a particular focus on comparing instrumental and integrative motivation. Employing a quantitative research design, data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to 90 students selected via systematic random sampling across the 2nd, 6th, and 8th semesters of the Department of English. Descriptive statistical analysis using SPSS revealed that motivation significantly enhances various dimensions of language acquisition, including academic success, fostering interest in English learning, regular practice of language skills, language-related memory retainment, and social interactions. Motivation impacts English language learning by developing self-efficacy in English learning, language autonomy, proficiency, and fluency in English. It helps to overcome language learning anxiety, face challenges related to language learning, and build confidence to speak English. Motivation helps learners to stay focused, engaged, and actively participate in English language classes. Although learners exhibited both integrative and instrumental motivational factors, the findings indicate a pronounced prevalence of instrumental motivation—driven by the pursuit of better educational opportunities, career advancement, professional skill development, societal expectations, and prospects for travel abroad. This suggests that, for these students, English is primarily viewed as a pragmatic tool for achieving academic and professional objectives rather than as a means of cultural integration. The study fills an existing gap in the literature regarding motivational impacts in rural

educational settings and recommends that language curricula and teaching methodologies be tailored to better align with the instrumental goals of students. Future research might explore further the interplay between intrinsic, extrinsic, and technology-assisted learning motivations in diverse educational contexts.

Keywords: *Motivation, Instrumental Motivation, Integrative Motivation, Undergraduate Students, English Learning.*

INTRODUCTION

English is a global language spoken by people all over the world. It is a common medium of communication with over 1.5 billion people speaking worldwide. English language learning is a complex and fascinating process. The process is influenced by a combination of a dynamic set of multiple interconnected factors, such as motivation, attitudes toward language, learning environment, and teaching methodology. Motivation is one of the pivotal and core elements that have a substantial influence on this process. Motivation can be defined as a dynamic inner mechanism that progressively evokes, modulates, and perpetuates responses (Salvin, 2001). According to Woolfolk (1998), motivation is a dynamic psychological intrinsic state that arouses, directs, maintains, and reinforces the behaviour. Motivation empowers students towards language learning by keeping their interest alive. It acts as a catalyst that turns passive students into active participants in language learning. Motivation is a prerequisite for success in the end, and it significantly influences the students' engagement, persistence, and success in learning the English language by interacting with their language studies, engaging in all class activities, completing assignments on time, and seeking ways to practice more outside of the classroom. Their open-mindedness and readiness to accept the challenges of learning a language, grappling with new grammatical forms, expanding their vocabulary, etc., are much easier to enlist. Motivation influences the language system through these three channels: cognitive, affective, and behavioural. The first of these is cognitive, determining how learners will directly approach learning and retaining language knowledge. If the level of motivation is high, it is easier to focus attention and concentrate on the task, there will be more production in a shorter time, and learning will be more effective. Cognitive aspects of the motivation learning process involve the complex neuropsychological processes that influence how learners use their cognitive resources in the construction of linguistic knowledge. Dornyei (2005) L2MSS explains the essence of self-concept in developing sustained effort, where an ideal L2 image triggers continued mental effort. To what extent learners deal with linguistic challenges resiliently is determined by motivational constructs such as self-efficacy, epistemic curiosity (desire to obtain new knowledge), meta-cognitive regulation (the actions learners take to monitor, control, and adjust their thinking processes while learning by planning, monitoring and evaluating), cognitive dissonance resolution (process of resolving the mental discomfort like confusion, logical conflict with new information that conflicts with existing information) and reflective praxis (process of actively reflecting on experiences and actions to improve future practice and understanding) by strengthening neural links between cognitive effort and language proficiency. Motivation drives cognitive adaptability to interact, resulting in a dynamic learning path, while attentional control, strategic competence, and self-regulated learning promote linguistic proficiency. Affective aspects of motivation are related to

impressions and emotions about English learning. Motivating factors are also associated with feelings of pleasure, interest, and confidence. The affective factors of English language learning synthesize the complex relations between emotional valences, psychological robustness (an individual capacity to withstand and adapt to challenges, stress, and adversity, and maintain mental well-being and functionality), and socio-affective mechanisms driving linguistic investment. Behavioural aspects of motivation influence the actions, activities, choices, and decisions of learners to learn the language. This motivates people to learn more consistently on their own with a lot of self-direction and participation in learning. Motivation in English learning refers to engagement, persistence, and strategic interaction with the language.

According to Gardner (1985), there are two types of motivations. Instrumental motivation deals with practical benefits like career growth and academic success. When learners develop instrumental motivation, they are interested in how language proficiency will help them reach specific goals. Learners with integrative motivation want to connect with the target language community and culture. They have a passion for interacting with native speakers as well as immersing themselves in the language. According to Deci & Ryan (2000), intrinsic motivation refers to the type of motivation where an individual is motivated by the elements from within, based on their interest and enjoyment, or feels some kind of fulfillment. Extrinsic motivation refers to motivation due to external factors, including rewards, obligations, or recognition.

In Pakistan, English is not just another subject that is taught in schools and universities; it is a must-have subject for academic success and professional progress by guiding the student's educational and career trajectory (Nawaz et al., 2015). Motivation in ELL influences learners' cognitive engagement, emotional responses, and behavioral patterns. Motivation helps cognitively improve the attention, memory retention, and problem-solving skills of learners to process and internalise linguistic information (Khurshid, 2021). For many undergraduate students, especially those from rural backgrounds, motivation is a problem due to the lack of access to qualified instructors and language support systems. Many learners arrive at university with a varied level of exposure to English, which impacts their confidence and willingness to participate in language learning at university. How universities can become partners in motivation for ELL depends on these types of policies that promote such language learning initiatives (Mahmood and Yaseen, 2022). Various researchers and scholars have done their research on the impacts of motivation and comparatively analysed different types of motivation among EFL and ESL students but examining the impacts of motivation on English language learning at ULM and identifying the prevalent type of motivation (INM and IM) for English language learning among undergraduates students at ULM, and specifically in Department of English have been left unexplored so far. Considering the gap in the existing literature, the current study delves into how motivation impacts English language learning and which type of motivation (INM and IM) is prevalent among English undergraduates at the ULM.

The following are the research objectives:

- i. To identify the impacts of motivation on learning English at the Department of English, ULM.

- ii. To identify the prevalent types of motivation (INM and IM) among undergraduate students for English language learning at the Department of English, ULM.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Learning a non-native language is a complex and multifarious process significantly influenced by numerous factors. Among these, motivation is one of the cardinal forces that propel language learners' enthusiasm, sustain perseverance, and shape smooth trajectories for language learning. Lamb (2012) study explored global motivation for English learning, particularly in EFL contexts where English is not widely spoken. He found that instrumental motivation dominates, and students consider English to be a gateway to academic and professional success, suggesting that economic incentives primarily drive learners. His research examined Indonesian secondary school students, using longitudinal interviews and proficiency tests to analyse motivational patterns. Findings revealed that while globalisation has increased learners' awareness of English's importance, motivation fluctuates depending on perceived usefulness and classroom experience. Through the study of Csizér and Dornyei (2005), instrumental motivation turned out to be the best predictor of success in the case of Hungarian EFL learners. Their research found that learners who viewed English as a means of career advancement were more motivated compared to the integrative motivated ones. The research participants were high school learning using questionnaires and proficiency tests. MacIntyre and Gardner (1991) investigated the relationship between motivation and language anxiety, finding that motivated learners experience lower anxiety and exhibit greater resilience in learning. Their study examined how affective factors influence SLA and showed that motivation is a buffer against learning-related stress. The findings suggested that positive attitudes toward learning helped students cope with anxiety and maintain persistence. The study involved Canadian students learning French as an L2. Researchers used self-report questionnaires and anxiety scales to measure motivation levels alongside performance tests. The results indicated that students with motivation exhibited lower anxiety levels, reinforcing the importance of motivation in SLA success. Csizér and Kormos (2009) examined the impact of parental pressure on English language learning and found that students motivated by parental influence to achieve success demonstrated higher engagement in language learning. The study involved Hungarian EFL students, using focus groups and proficiency assessments. Results suggested that parental pressure to achieve higher proficiency plays a critical role in shaping motivation, particularly in EFL learners. Iqbal et al. (2025) probe the variables that affect the University of Lakki Marwat undergraduate students' motivation to learn English in Chemistry, the English and Mathematics departments. It found important motivators, including technological implementation, culturally responsive resources, faculty training, efficient instructional techniques, pliable instructional aid, personal goal-setting, optimal setting, and a student-centred approach.

Lai (1999) research found that focusing on career goals, instrumental motivation was found in Hong Kong Chinese EFL students. Research reveals that university students are more likely to be motivated by instruments than by the chance to read and speak in another language. A lot of students believe that a good knowledge of English can

improve their academic results, open new career paths, and help them travel the world. For some individuals, English helps them meet friends from different backgrounds, though this is usually less important than learning English for its usefulness. Taimouri et al. (2014) affirm that motivation explicitly impacts students' engagement and maintains proficiency. Research examining the students' views on the target language country can motivate them during language learning at the University of Malaysia. The research looks into whether integrative motivation influences the learning of foreign languages. According to the study, students were integratively motivated to learn English, and they wanted to interact with the English community and culture. Dornyei (2005) introduced the L2MSS, which emphasises the role of self-concept in language learning motivation. His study found that learners with a strong vision of their future selves as proficient English speakers exhibited higher engagement and persistence in learning. The study surveyed Hungarian EFL learners, analysing their motivation through questionnaires and interviews. The findings suggested that the Ideal L2 Self, representing a learner's aspirations, was a powerful predictor of motivation. External expectations (Ought-to L2 Self) influenced motivation but to a lesser extent. Oxford and Shearin (1994) explored long-term motivation in language learning, emphasising the importance of intrinsic motivation. Their study found that intrinsically motivated learners, driven by personal interest and enjoyment, engaged in deeper cognitive processing and retained language skills more effectively. The study involved college students learning foreign languages using surveys and classroom observations. The results highlighted that goal-setting and self-regulation were crucial in sustaining motivation over time. Ushioda (2001) research was based on the areas of learner autonomy and its influence on motivation. She discovered that self-motivated learners (who took ownership of their learning rather than giving in to external persuasions) outperformed those who learned because of external incentives (i.e., gifts and rewards). Her research studied university students learning English through qualitative interviews and self-reflection journals. The outcomes highlighted that personal agency and intrinsic motivation would play a significant role in effective language acquisition. Noels et al. (2000) showed that intrinsically motivated learners displayed better retention rates and better engagement. The study surveyed a total of 159 adult learners of French and recorded their motivation levels on a learning outcome. The findings indicate that autonomy-supportive learning environments encouraged intrinsic motivation that resulted in a better language level as its end product. Ryan and Deci (2000) SDT highlighted the importance of autonomy in fostering intrinsic motivation. Their study found that learners who had control over their learning process exhibited higher engagement and persistence. The study examined college students learning Spanish, using experimental methods to assess motivation levels.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research paradigm of research work is positivism and the research approach for the study is quantitative. The individuals participating in this study are 90 undergraduate students from the Department of English at ULM, selected through systematic random sampling, 30 students from each of the 2nd, 6th, and 8th semesters, with an equal division of 15 male and 15 female students in each semester. The data was collected through a structured questionnaire. The

questionnaire includes 25 statements with broad questions as well as specific items reflecting motivational impacts on English language learning and determining the prevalent type of motivation in the English Department, at ULM.

DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

The collected data was analyzed through SPSS. The compiled data was treated by the Descriptive Statistical analysis using SPSS. For each item, we computed frequency, percentage, and cumulative percentage, and we presented these values in separate tables that showed the final results of the analysis. The Likert scale provided the options of strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree to the respondents.

4.1. Role of Motivation in Academic Success

Motivation is beneficial throughout the learning process as it keeps learners on target. For the students in this study, motivation was seen as a critical factor in helping students achieve their academic goals, not only by helping them to learn good study habits but also by guiding them through barriers they encounter in their studies and sustaining their efforts toward academic success.

Table 1. Motivation plays a crucial role in my academic success.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	45	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Agree	37	41.1	41.1	91.1
	Neutral	8	8.9	8.9	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 1, 50.0% of students strongly agree, 41.1% agree, and 8.9% are neutral with the statement.

4.2. Motivation Foster's Interest in English Language Learning

Motivation impacts the learning process in many ways, and one is by fostering interest in English language learning. The recent research illustrates that motivation encourages students to dive deeply into getting knowledge about English language learning, exploring new information, and making opportunities to practice English.

Table 2. Motivation fosters my interest in English language learning.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	35	38.9	38.9	38.9
	Agree	46	51.1	51.1	90.0
	Neutral	7	7.8	7.8	97.8
	Disagree	2	2.2	2.2	100.0

Total	90	100.0	100.0
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The result of Table 2 shows that 38.9% of students strongly agree, 51.1% agree, 7.8% are neutral, and 2.2% disagree.

4.3. Motivation Helps to Practice English Skills Regularly

Motivation is a key factor in English learning. According to the responses from the study’s questionnaire, students highlighted that motivation serves to bolster regulated learning of those particular skills of reading, writing, speaking, and listening.

Table 3. Motivation helps me to practice English language skills regularly.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	32	35.6	35.6	35.6
	Agree	35	38.9	38.9	74.4
	Neutral	18	20.0	20.0	94.4
	Disagree	5	5.6	5.6	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 3, statistics, 35.6 % of students strongly agree, 38.9% agree, 20% are neutral, and only 5.6% disagree with the statement.

4.4. Motivation Helps to Develop Social Interaction in English

Motivation is of absolute importance for improving social interactions in English. Motivated learners seek out opportunities to interview, discuss, and collaboratively exchange. Most students in the research revealed that motivation is a key driver in developing social interactions in English.

Table 4. Motivation helps me to develop my social interactions in English.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	32	35.6	35.6	35.6
	Agree	42	46.7	46.7	82.2
	Neutral	10	11.1	11.1	93.3
	Disagree	5	5.6	5.6	98.9
	Strongly Disagree	1	1.1	1.1	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

The data presented in Table 4 indicate that 35.6% of students strongly agree, 46.7% agree, 11.1% are neutral, 5.6% disagree, and 1.1% strongly disagree.

4.5. Motivations Help to Stay Focused and Engaged in English Language Classes

Motivation plays a central role in motivating learners to follow through in English language classes, always with the same participation, thus ensuring efficient learning. The students’ data analysis shows that the feeling of motivation helps to cultivate persistence that will keep them attentive even when learning a tough concept, grammar, or difficult vocabulary.

Table 5. Motivation helps me to stay focused and engaged in English language classes.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	38	42.2	42.2	42.2
	Agree	33	36.7	36.7	78.9
	Neutral	12	13.3	13.3	92.2
	Disagree	7	7.8	7.8	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 5 illustrates that 42.2% strongly agree, 36.7% agree, 13.3% are neutral, and 7.8% disagree that they are focused and engaged due to motivation during English language classes.

4.6. Motivation Improves English Language-Related Memory Retainment

A potent level of motivation greatly improves the retention of memory in English language studies. The research finding suggests that motivated learners are interested in language learning by nature or self-development; they read the material more deeply, which results in understanding, long-term retention, and commitment towards committing data such as vocabulary, grammatical structures, and communication patterns.

Table 6. Motivation improves the English language-related memory retainment (vocabulary, grammatical rules, idiomatic expressions).

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	25	27.8	27.8	27.8
	Agree	37	41.1	41.1	68.9
	Neutral	19	21.1	21.1	90.0
	Disagree	8	8.9	8.9	98.9
	Strongly Disagree	1	1.1	1.1	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 6 confirms that 27.8% strongly agree, 41.1% agree, 21.1% are neutral, 8.9% disagree, and 1.1% strongly disagree with the statement.

4.7. Motivation Helps to Build Confidence in Speaking English

Confidence in speaking English has an extremely strong relationship with the level of motivation of learners. Recent study show that a motivated person is going to try looking for opportunities for real-world conversations, participating in discussions, as well as pushing himself to speak even if he may be wrong.

Table 7. Motivation helps me build confidence in speaking English.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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Valid	Strongly Agree	43	47.8	47.8	47.8
	Agree	33	36.7	36.7	84.4
	Neutral	12	13.3	13.3	97.8
	Disagree	1	1.1	1.1	98.9
	Strongly Disagree	1	1.1	1.1	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

47.8% strongly agree, while 36.7% agree, as shown in Table 7. Moreover, 13.3% remain neutral, only 1.1% disagree and 1.1% strongly disagree with the statement.

4.8. Motivation is a great force that overcomes the difficulties in learning English.

The process of learning a new language is usually accompanied by difficulties with complex grammatical rules, unrecognised vocabulary, obstacles with pronunciation, and sometimes frustration. However, this research reveals that a motivated learner faces these challenges, seeing them as a chance for enhancements and an opportunity, not as an obstacle.

Table 8. Motivation helps me to face challenges related to learning English.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	32	35.6	35.6	35.6
	Agree	39	43.3	43.3	78.9
	Neutral	8	8.9	8.9	87.8
	Disagree	9	10.0	10.0	97.8
	Strongly Disagree	2	2.2	2.2	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 8 shows that 35.6% of students strongly agree, 43.3% agree, 8.9% are neutral, 10% disagree, and 2.2% strongly disagree.

4.9. Motivation Helps to Participate in English Language Classes

Motivation is very important to the learning of the English language because it affects not only linguistic but also non-linguistic factors as well. Students in the study show that motivation helps them to participate in English language classes.

Table 9. Motivation helps me to participate in English language classes.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	29	32.2	32.2	32.2
	Agree	40	44.4	44.4	76.7
	Neutral	17	18.9	18.9	95.6
	Disagree	3	3.3	3.3	98.9
	Strongly Disagree	1	1.1	1.1	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 9 shows the distribution of responses, 32.2% strongly agree, 44.4% agree, 18.9% remained undecided, and only 3.3% and 1.1% disagree and strongly disagree respectively.

4.10. Motivation Helps to Overcome Language Learning Anxiety

Motivation is the determinant of overcoming language learning anxiety, which will make learners acquire confident and resilient personalities. The students opine that there is a lot of anxiety in learning a language might be either the fear of mistakes, the difficulty with pronunciation, or the experience of difficulty communicating. Motivation helps develop adaptability, which allows motivated learners to overcome setbacks with ambition, not discouragement, develops positive attitude to learning that relieve anxiety and promote relaxed behaviour toward English language learning.

Table 10. Motivation helps me to overcome language learning anxiety.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	34	37.8	37.8	37.8
	Agree	33	36.7	36.7	74.4
	Neutral	19	21.1	21.1	95.6
	Disagree	3	3.3	3.3	98.9
	Strongly Disagree	1	1.1	1.1	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 10 highlights the results that 37.8% strongly agree, 36.7% agree, 21.1% remain neutral, 3.3% disagree, and 1.1% strongly disagree with the above statement.

4.11. Motivation Enhances Self-Efficacy in English Language Learning

Motivation makes self-efficacy considerably more powerful in English language study, thus empowering the learners to have unleashed convictions in their ability to succeed. The majority of students acknowledge that motivation enhances their self-efficacy in language learning.

Table 11. Motivation enhances my self-efficacy in English language learning.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	27	30.0	30.0	30.0
	Agree	44	48.9	48.9	78.9
	Neutral	16	17.8	17.8	96.7
	Disagree	1	1.1	1.1	97.8
	Strongly Disagree	2	2.2	2.2	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 11 reveals that 30.0% strongly agree, 48.9% agree, 17.8% are neutral, 1.1% disagree, and 2.2% strongly disagree.

4.12. Motivation Improves English Language Autonomy

Motivation is an integral part of building learner autonomy in English language learning. The study data implies that motivation encourages learners to make

independent learning decisions, set their goals, define their skills development, and improve their approach according to self-assessment.

Table 12. Motivation improves my English language autonomy.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	23	25.6	25.6	25.6
	Agree	40	44.4	44.4	70.0
	Neutral	18	20.0	20.0	90.0
	Disagree	9	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

It is clear from Table 12 that 25.6% of students strongly agree, 44.4% agree, 20.0% are neutral, and 10.0% disagree that motivation improves their English language autonomy.

4.13. Motivation Improves English Fluency and Proficiency

Motivation is of great significance in improving fluency and proficiency in the English language. Fluency is the power to play out ideas with fluidity and ease while proficiency is the extent of comprehension and knowledge of linguistic structures. The study discovered that when learners are motivated, they look for ways to be immersed in English.

Table 13. Motivation improves my fluency and proficiency in English.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	29	32.2	32.2	32.2
	Agree	47	52.2	52.2	84.4
	Neutral	7	7.8	7.8	92.2
	Disagree	4	4.4	4.4	96.7
	Strongly Disagree	3	3.3	3.3	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

The results in Table 13 show that 32.2% strongly agree, 52.2% agree, 7.8% are neutral, 4.4% disagree, and 3.3% strongly disagree.

4.14. Integrative Motivation to Learn English due to Interest in English as a Language

Integrative motivation is a drive to acquire language due to interest in the language itself, language culture, or its community. The study strongly indicates that students are highly motivated to learn English because of their love for English as a language and to achieve personal satisfaction related to English.

Table 14. I am motivated to learn English due to my interest in English as a language.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	45	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Agree	36	40.0	40.0	90.0
	Neutral	5	5.6	5.6	95.6
	Disagree	3	3.3	3.3	98.9
	Strongly Disagree	1	1.1	1.1	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 14 demonstrates that 50% strongly agree, 40% agree, 5.6% are neutral, 3.3% disagree, and 1.1% strongly disagree.

4.15. Integrative Motivation to Learn English to Appreciate English Literature

English literature provides rich, recognised literature with centuries of tales, thoughts, and world points of view. The study finds that learning English through literary appreciation develops critical thinking abilities, thereby giving the ability to interpret symbolic language, analyse character progression, and engage with the literature.

Table 15. I am motivated to learn English to appreciate English literature.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	24	26.7	26.7	26.7
	Agree	29	32.2	32.2	58.9
	Neutral	18	20.0	20.0	78.9
	Disagree	15	16.7	16.7	95.6
	Strongly Disagree	4	4.4	4.4	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 15 illustrates that 26.7% strongly agree, 32.2 % agree, 20% remain neutral, 16.7% disagree, and 4.4% strongly disagree.

4.16. Integrative Motivation to Learn English to Build Relationships with English-speaking Communities

Language is a link to valuable relationships, and learning to speak English has a great impact on building deeper relationships with the English natives. The research suggests that by increasing fluency, they can bond on a personal level with an English-speaking friend, colleague, or academic peer so that conversations become more meaningful and pleasurable.

Table 16. I am motivated to learn English to build deeper relationships with English-speaking communities.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	16	17.8	17.8	17.8
	Agree	39	43.3	43.3	61.1
	Neutral	26	28.9	28.9	90.0
	Disagree	7	7.8	7.8	97.8

Strongly Disagree	2	2.2	2.2	100.0
Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 16 shows that 17.8 % strongly agree, 43.3% agree, 28.9% remain neutral, 7.8% disagree, and 2.2% strongly disagree with the statement.

4.17. Integrative Motivation for Learning English to Understand English Music & TV Shows

For a convivial experience of artistic expression, English language music and television are endless resources. The students surveyed show that they are motivated to learn English to understand and enjoy English music and Television shows.

Table 17. I am motivated to learn English to understand the English language, music, and TV shows.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	22	24.4	24.4	24.4
	Agree	28	31.1	31.1	55.6
	Neutral	22	24.4	24.4	80.0
	Disagree	16	17.8	17.8	97.8
	Strongly Disagree	2	2.2	2.2	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

As evident from Table 17, 24.4% strongly agree, 31.1% agree, 24.4% are neutral, 17.8% disagree, and 2.2% strongly disagree with the statement.

4.18. Integrative Motivation to Learn English to Connect with Diverse Cross-Cultural Background People

An integrative force that is high has a huge impact on the success of people in learning English as a second language. Study reveals that integrative motivation to connect with diverse cultural backgrounds globally enhances learners' ability to develop strong communicative skills and more interactions in the English language.

Table 18. I am motivated to learn English to connect with people from diverse cross-cultural backgrounds.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	31	34.4	34.4	34.4
	Agree	43	47.8	47.8	82.2
	Neutral	14	15.6	15.6	97.8
	Disagree	2	2.2	2.2	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

It is clear from Table 18 that 34.4% of students strongly agree, 47.8% agree, 15.6% are neutral, and just 2.2% disagree with the statement.

4.19. Integrative Motivation to Learn English to Understand & Appreciate English Cultural Heritage

A substantial number of students are inclined to study English to understand the cultural heritage of English to a greater extent. Most students agreed, with a notable proportion neutral, that they are motivated to learn English, learning to understand and appreciate English cultural heritage like Western civilisation, cultural expressions, norms, and values.

Table 19. I am motivated to learn English to understand and appreciate the English cultural heritage (Western civilisation, cultural expressions, norms, values).

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	20	22.2	22.2	22.2
	Agree	23	25.6	25.6	47.8
	Neutral	17	18.9	18.9	66.7
	Disagree	23	25.6	25.6	92.2
	Strongly Disagree	7	7.8	7.8	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 19 reveals that 22.2% strongly agree, 25.6% agree, 18.9% are neutral, 25.6% disagree, and 7.8% strongly disagree with the statement.

4.20. Instrumental Motivation to Learn English to Access Better Education Opportunities

Learning the English language means that students get access to a vast amount of high-quality educational information and enter famous academies and international academic programs. Study reveals that good English teaches effective communication with faculty, students, and researchers, which helps in academic improvement and better educational opportunities.

Table 20. I am motivated to learn English to access better educational opportunities (higher education, scholarships).

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	45	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Agree	37	41.1	41.1	91.1
	Neutral	5	5.6	5.6	96.7
	Disagree	3	3.3	3.3	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 20 outlines that 50% strongly agree, 41.1% agree, 5.6% are neutral, and only 3.3% disagree with the statement.

4.21. Instrumental Motivation to Learn English for Career Advancement

For undergraduate students learning English, motivation is of great importance, engendering their involvement and outcome, particularly when career advancement is one of the biggest facilitators. The majority of students realise that the command of English opens a wider range of professional possibilities, including an international career, competitive job placement, and positions requiring cross-cultural communication.

Table 21. I am motivated to learn English for career advancement.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	46	51.1	51.1	51.1
	Agree	33	36.7	36.7	87.8
	Neutral	10	11.1	11.1	98.9
	Disagree	1	1.1	1.1	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 21 reveals that 87.8% of students want to learn English to advance their career opportunities, 11.1% are neutral, and only 1.1% disagree with the above statement.

4.22. Instrumental Motivation to Learn English to Meet Societal Expectations

Driven by norms, many learners incorporate their English studies to learn to be fluent and acquire a specific accent. Research shows that it is well known in many cultures that getting fluent in English unlocks the door to more prestige, and social acceptance on a worldwide scale.

Table 22. I am motivated to learn English to meet societal expectations (fluency, accent).

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	32	35.6	35.6	35.6
	Agree	41	45.6	45.6	81.1
	Neutral	11	12.2	12.2	93.3
	Disagree	6	6.7	6.7	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 22 represents the results that 35.6% strongly agree, 45.6% agree, 12.2% remain neutral, and only 6.7% disagree with the statement.

4.23. Instrumental Motivation to Learn English to Improve Professional Skills

Instrumental motivation is extremely important in the motivation of undergraduates to acquire professional English skills because they recognise the ability to use language as a practical weapon for establishing a successful career. Recent shows that motivation improves students' professional skills to learn English.

Table 23. I am motivated to learn English to improve my professional skills.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	41	45.6	45.6	45.6
	Agree	34	37.8	37.8	83.3
	Neutral	10	11.1	11.1	94.4
	Disagree	5	5.6	5.6	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 23 illustrates that 83.3% agree while 11.1% are neutral and 5.6% disagree with the above statement.

4.24. Instrumental Motivation to Learn English due to Parental Pressure

Parental pressure can be one of the great influential factors related to the motivation of undergraduate students of the English language. Many students in the study reveal that if parental encouragement makes for discipline and structure, too much pressure can lead to anxiety or a lack of intrinsic motivation. The majority of the students agree that there is no parental pressure on them to study English.

Table 24. I am motivated to learn English due to parental pressure (for high grades and a good job).

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	16	17.8	17.8	17.8
	Agree	13	14.4	14.4	32.2
	Neutral	13	14.4	14.4	46.7
	Disagree	32	35.6	35.6	82.2
	Strongly Disagree	16	17.8	17.8	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 24 illustrates that 32.2% agree, 14.4% are neutral while the majority 35.6%, and 17.8% disagree and strongly disagree respectively with the statement.

4.25. Instrumental Motivation to Learn English to Travel Abroad

For the undergraduate studying English, travel abroad could be a strong motivator for study. Most students acknowledge that this skill will make their interaction within and outside the international space easier and offer them a better chance at academic exchange, professional exposure, or cultural exposure.

Table 25. I am motivated to learn English to travel abroad.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	20	22.2	22.2	22.2
	Agree	36	40.0	40.0	62.2
	Neutral	18	20.0	20.0	82.2
	Disagree	8	8.9	8.9	91.1
	Strongly Disagree	8	8.9	8.9	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Table 25 shows that 22.2% strongly agree, 40% agree, 20% of students are neutral, while only 8.9% disagree and 8.9% strongly disagree with the above statement.

4.26. Frequency Difference between Integrative and Instrumental Motivation among ULM English Undergraduate Students

Table 1. Integrative Motivation among English Undergraduate Students at ULM

No	Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD	Total
1	Interest in English as a language	45	36	5	3	1	90
2	Appreciate English literature	24	29	18	15	4	90
3	Build a relationship with the English community	16	39	26	7	2	90
4	Understand English music and TV shows	22	28	22	16	2	90

5	Connect with people from diverse cultures	31	43	14	2	0	90
6	Understand and appreciate English cultural heritage	20	23	17	23	7	90
Total		158	198	102	66	16	540

Table 2. Instrumental Motivation among English Undergraduate Students at ULM

No	Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD	Total
1	Better educational opportunities	45	37	5	3	0	90
2	Career advancement	46	33	10	1	0	90
3	Meet societal expectations	32	41	11	6	0	90
4	Improve professional skills	41	34	10	5	0	90
5	Due to parental pressure	16	13	13	32	16	90
6	Travel abroad	20	36	18	8	8	90
Total		200	194	67	55	24	540

Table 1 and Table 2 show the frequency difference between integrative and instrumental motivation among English undergraduates at ULM indicating a clear prevalence of instrumental motivation.

Discussions

The study aims to investigate the impacts of motivation on English language learning in the context of Lakki Marwat. This study comparatively analyses IN and INM, to identify prevalent type of motivation among English undergraduates at the University of Lakki Marwat. Csizér and Dornyei (2005), Lamb (2012), and (Lai, 1999) found instrumental motivation as a prevalent type of motivation that ensures academic and professional success. The present study is similar to the previously mentioned researches because they all found instrumental motivation as the dominant type of motivation that students use to achieve success. MacIntyre and Gardner (1991) investigated the relationship between motivation and language anxiety, finding that motivated learners experience lower anxiety and exhibit greater resilience in learning. Both studies' findings align as they find that motivation improves language-related anxiety and helps students learn English more effectively.

Despite these similarities, there are notable differences when considering the factors in the motivation process. This contrasts with Csizér and Kormos (2009), who found parental pressure to be a dominant factor in motivation among language learners while this study found that parental pressure is not a dominant motivator for English language learning among English undergraduate students at ULM. The findings of the current study and Taimouri et al. (2014) findings are in contrast because they found integrative motivation as a dominant type of motivation among university students, while this study found instrumental motivation as the prevalent type of motivation among English undergraduate students. Iqbal et al. (2025) found important motivators, including technological implementation, culturally responsive resources, faculty training, efficient instructional techniques, pliable instructional aid, personal goal-setting, optimal setting, and a student-centred approach. The recent study is different from the previous one because the recent study investigates the impacts of motivation on English language learning, while the previous one studied the impacts of different factors like teaching tools, learning resources, and environmental, and academic aspects on motivation to learn the English.

CONCLUSION

This research investigated the impacts of motivation on studying the English language among the English undergraduates of ULM, emphasising the comparative analysis between integrative and instrumental motivation. To achieve this aim, previously done studies were critically analysed, and a systematic methodology was implemented to answer these two research questions:

- i. What are the impacts of motivation on English language learning at the Department of English, ULM?
- ii. Which type of motivation (INM and IM) is more prevalent among undergraduate students for English language learning at the Department of English, ULM?

The study uncovered a set of findings regarding the first research question, indicating that there are major and notable impacts of motivation on English language learning. Motivation plays a significant role in the academic success of learners by fostering their interest in English language learning. Motivation helps them to regularly practice language skills, develop social interactions in English, build their confidence to speak English, and stay focused and engaged during English language classes. Motivation impacts their cognitive ability to retain English-related knowledge for a long time as recalling hard vocabulary, idioms, or grammatical rules. Motivation helps them face challenges related to English language learning. It helps learners to actively participate in classroom activities, overcome language learning anxiety, and enhance their self-efficacy for learning English. Motivation improves and develops their language autonomy, improves their proficiency, and maximises their fluency in English.

Concerning the second research question, findings reveal that instrumental motivation is more prevalent among English undergraduate students in ULM than integrative motivation. Students are instrumentally motivated to learn English to get better educational opportunities, career advancement, societal expectations, professional skills improvement, and travel abroad. On the other hand, integrative motivation is evident, but seems more like a secondary influence, as students admit they are interested in English as a language, English literature, media, building relationships with the English community, cultural heritage, and cross-cultural communication and career advancement, and to polish their professional skills in English.

REFERENCES

- Csizér, K., & Dörnyei, Z. (2005). Language learners' motivational profiles and their motivated learning behaviour. *Language Learning*, 55(4), 613-659. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0023-8333.2005.00319.x>
- Csizér, K., & Kormos, J. (2009). Modelling the role of intercultural contact in the motivation of learning English as a foreign language. *Applied Linguistics*, 30(2), 166–185. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/amn025>
- Dörnyei, Z. (2005). *The psychology of the language learner: Individual differences in second language acquisition*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Gardner, R. C. (1985). *Social psychology and second language learning: The role of attitudes and motivation*. Edward Arnold.
- Iqbal, S. W., Jehan, K., Ullah, F., & Khan, A. (2025). Cracking the code of English learning: A case study of motivation among undergraduate students at the University

- of Lakki Marwat. *International Journal of Social Sciences Bulletin*, 3(3). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14968572>
- Khurshid, A. (2021). Cognitive and affective factors in English language learning motivation. *South Asian Linguistics Review*, 4(1), 22-38.
- Lai, C. (1999). An investigation of the relationship between motivation and achievement in EFL learning. *Journal of Language System*, 27(1), 111-125.
- Lamb, M. (2012). A self-system perspective on young adolescents' motivation to learn English in urban and rural settings. *Language Learning*, 62(4), 997-1023. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9922.2012.00719.x>
- MacIntyre, P. D., & Gardner, R. C. (1991). Language anxiety: Its relationship to other anxieties and to processing in native and second languages. *Language Learning*, 41(4), 513-534. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-1770.1991.tb00691.x>
- Mahmood, R., & Yaseen, T. (2022). Motivational dynamics in ELL: Institutional and pedagogical implications. *Asian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 10(2), 56-79. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-1770.1991.tb00691.x>
- Nawaz, S., Hassan, B., & Ali, F. (2015). English language learning motivation in Pakistani higher education institutions. *Pakistan Journal of Language Studies*, 3(2), 88-104.
- Noels, K. A., Pelletier, L. G., Clement, R., & Vallerand, R. J. (2000). Why are you learning a second language? Motivational orientations and self-determination theory. *Language Learning*, 50(1), 57-85. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0023-8333.00111>
- Oxford, R. & Shearin, J. (1994) Language learning motivation: Expanding the theoretical framework. *The Modern Language Journal*, 78(1), 12-28.
- Papi, M., & Teimouri, Y. (2014). Language learner motivational types: A cluster analysis study. *Language Learning*, 64(3), 493-525. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lang.12065>
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55(1), 68-78. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.55.1.68>
- Salvin, J. (2001). Effect of achievement motivation on scholastic achievement among High school girls. *Journal of Research in Education & Psychology*, 23(13), 123-32.
- Ushioda, E. (2001). Language learning at university: Exploring the role of motivational thinking. *Journal of Motivation and Second Language Acquisition*, 23, 91-121.
- Woolfolk, A. E. (1998). *Educational Psychology* (7th ed.). Allyn & Bacon.